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TYPOLOGY OF URBAN PLANNING PLACEMENT OF PUBLIC CATERING FACILITIES

Abstract: The article considers the main options for urban planning- шенияof public catering facilities with the identification of their characteristic features. There are nine types of PLO locations in the city structure. The analytical base includes domestic and зару- бежныеforeign restaurants that opened not earlier than 2009.

Key words: public catering facilities, typologyof urban-construction placement, city, building, territory.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada shaharsozlikning asosiy variantlari ko'rib chiqiladi - umumiy ovqatlanish ob'ektlarining xarakterli xususiyatlarini aniqlagan holda. Shahar tuzilmasida FLOning to'qqiz turi mavjud. Analitik bazaga 2009 yildan oldin ochilgan mahalliy va xorijiy restoranlar kiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: umumiy ovqatlanish ob'ektlari, shahar-qurilishni joylashtirish tipologiyasi, shahar, bino, hudud.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены основные варианты городского планирова- ния объектов общественного питания с выявлением их характерных особенностей. В структуре города выделено девять типов мест размещения объектов общественного питания. Аналитическая база включает отечественные и зарубежные рестораны, открывшиеся не ранее 2009 года.

Ключевые слова: объекты общественного питания, типология градостроительного размещения, город, здание, территория.

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Public catering facilities (PSOs) are now becoming increasingly important both as independent elements of the urban environment and in the structure of large, medium and small public buildings and complexes. Expanding the range of public catering facilities and changing their role in the social life of modern society — their development as centers of attraction for visitors and places of leisure - all this determines the interest in considering such objects in the planning structure of cities and other localities. Important factors affecting the provision of public catering to the population are the availability and attractiveness of public catering enterprises, their profitability and attendance, which directly depends on the location of these objects in the structure of cities and suburbs. Types and features of the location of public catering establishments have long been considered in the works of such authors as V. P. Urenev, T. T. Nikulenkova and others. However, the question of forming a modern urban planning typology for the placement of PLO remained open, since the dynamic growth of the public catering industry affected the emergence of new formats of establishments that were previously unknown, and, accordingly, the requirements for their placement in the city structure changed. Therefore, the purpose of this work is to generalize and systematize domestic and foreign experience in the placement of modern public catering facilities in the urban environment and to form on this basis a typology of urban planning placement of PLO. The subject of the study is the nature of the placement of PLO in the structure of the city, due to the type of PLO (free-standing/in the structure of a public building), the type of PLO object (full-cycle/pre-training, etc.), its service class, average passability, and whether it is linked to transport services. The material for this article is an analysis of urban planning placement of more than 48 public catering facilities in Russia, Europe, Eastern countries and the United States. As a result of the work done, nine most significant types of OOP placement

were identified. The following criteria, identified by the author as the basic ones as a result of a comparative analysis of design materials and buildings, are the basis for identifying the types of urban planning placement of PLO:

- * location in the city structure (center / periphery / recreational area / outside the city limits / linked to transport and pedestrian infrastructure / outrageous placement of objects, etc.);

- the presence or absence of large public objects in the immediate vicinity that are the centers of attraction for visitors; • the type of PLO object (cafe, restaurant, fast food, etc.).

The type of urban planning placement is identified by applying the selected criteria (and their characteristics) to the subject field (OOP placements) and fixing the most stable and repetitive combinations of the characteristics of each criterion with the OOP type. In the course of the work, a comprehensive approach was applied and the following research methods were used:

- * graphoanalytical method for analyzing planning solutions for placing PLO in the structure of settlements (working with object plans and building plans, maps of settlements (and their planning elements), transport diagrams);

- * a method of comparative analysis of design (drawings and diagrams describing the spatial and planning characteristics of the object) and factual materials (photos, advertising materials) that characterize the current experience of designing, building and operating PLO, on the basis of which the materials were systematized and conclusions were drawn about the planning features and frequency of placement of PLO in the settlement environment;

- * the typological method in its traditional sense, based on the identification of essential features (criteria) related to the subject field and which are the basis for identifying a reasonable minimum of types of urban planning placement of PLO;

- * a method for modeling the most typical situations of OOP placement and fixing them in

generalized graphical models of OOP placement in the settlement environment

As factual material for comparative analysis and typological procedures, domestic and foreign public catering facilities were taken. The criteria for selecting PLO objects were the year of opening of the institution (not earlier than 2009), the availability of project documentation for this object, belonging to the type of PLO that is often used in practice (this determines the reliability and verifiability of the result), and an expressive architectural and artistic solution. Author and country are additional information about the map item. It is impossible to demonstrate a complete analysis in a single article, so the paper presents the main and most characteristic points inherent in OOP. Based on a comparative analysis of the selected PLOS, determining the specifics and frequency of their placement in the settlement environment, conducting typological percents (justification, comparison and allocation of the minimum of basic types according to the criteria described above), nine main types of urban planning placement of public catering facilities were identified.

The first type of urban planning placement is a PLO in the city center near socially significant objects. This type of location is the most common and most popular. Most of the restaurants and cafes are located in the central areas of cities, which is due to the large number of offices, shops, as well as wider leisure opportunities compared to the outskirts.

The advantage of this type of PLO placement is its dominant position in the development, transport and pedestrian accessibility and high passability of people, and as a result-emphasized architectural expressiveness, but a significant limitation for this type of object location is the lack of free territory in the central part of the city, which is the reason for limiting the use of developed planning solutions and a wide variety of functional fillings. Large public catering facilities (restaurants, canteens) are located in the city center, as a rule,

as a result of a historically developed situation (possibly in the context of reconstruction/renovation with the preservation of the basic function). In general, the appearance of new large — format establishments in the central districts is very rare.

More mobile PLOS, small establishments that operate on semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness (cafes, bars, eateries, etc.), are more often opened in the central part of the city, replacing other public service enterprises. Due to the high level of competition, public catering facilities are forced to quickly respond to social requests and offer consumers new formats of establishments, increasing the variability of the public catering network.

Examples are the *Apetit* canteen in Ljubljana, Slovakia and the *Jardin de Jade* Restaurant in Shanghai, China. These objects are distinguished by their architectural expressiveness, they are located in the city center, all of them were built no earlier than 2009, all of them are not large and are placed as built-in-the first/ground floors (or introduced during the reconstruction/refunctionalization period).

The second type of urban planning placement is a PLO in a residential area of the city. The location of PLO in residential areas of the city in Russia is only gaining popularity, when in the West and in America this type of placement has long been used. The main advantage of this location is the availability of free territories and the focus of modern developers on the construction of multifunctional complexes, in the structure of which PLO objects appear. In this case (as in the previous one — placement in the city center), there is also a reconstruction of existing buildings with the arrangement of public catering facilities in the first and ground floors.

The location of public catering enterprises is linked to the overall spatial structure of all-terrain transport zones of the city so that these enterprises of regional significance complement the system of enterprises of citywide significance and are

included in the overall architectural and spatial structure of dominants, landmarks, and socially attractive places of the city. Due to the focus of public catering establishments located in residential areas on visitors from nearby houses, a specific feature of such PLOS is a small passability, depending on the time of day, days of the week and season. With this type of placement, small areas that have a memorable appearance are common, often mobile PLOS that work on semi-finished products. Examples include the Taiwan Noodle House cafe in Beijing, China, and La Grelha Cafe in Jalisco, Mexico — all of which meet the above criteria and were built after 2009.

The third type of urban planning placement is a PLO located outside the city limits. The modern layout of public catering facilities is dictated by the lack of space in the central part of the city. The remoteness of the object allows you to create large-format, multi-functional OOPS with a convenient infrastructure. Due to the limited transport accessibility, these catering establishments are focused on the long-term stay of visitors, so they offer a wide range of services (children's playgrounds, contact zoos, stables, shooting ranges, etc.). The possibility of using the surrounding natural environment or artificial components of the natural landscape makes it attractive for urban residents. Examples include Filandon restaurant, Madrid, Spain, and Podvorye restaurant, St. Petersburg, Russia.

The fourth type of urban planning placement is a PLO on highways. Public catering facilities are located in separate buildings or are part of a complex service station. The peculiarity of such enterprises is, on the one hand, fast service for some visitors and economical operation, moderate architectural and artistic advantages of the interiors and exteriors of structures, and on the other hand, the need to create conditions for longer recreation (mini-hotels, motels, rest rooms as part of the PLO objects), which imposes additional requirements for planning requirements. solutions of the object and territory (availability of parking

spaces for guests). Plos are usually located along the road or away from it, less often placed at road intersections. In the West, there are public catering facilities located above the highway with access from different directions. As an example, fast food chain restaurants (Subway, McDonald's, Autolanch) are located together with a gas station and recreation areas (mini-hotels).

The fifth type of urban planning placement is a PLO in a recreational area. The most favorable and attractive location option is when the item is located on the territory of a park, city garden, or bordering a body of water. Places with a high level of landscaping have always been the center of attraction for people. A special feature of this placement is the picturesque environmental solution, high environmental and aesthetic characteristics of the area, which are reflected in the architectural solution and appearance of the building. As a rule, such objects have pedestrian accessibility for visitors. Here, loading problems are additionally solved in the absence of mandatory transport links in protected natural areas. Such facilities usually operate on semi-finished products, and their production processes are minimized. The main thing in this case is to find a harmonious combination of architecture and nature, which in this context are equivalent parts of one whole. Examples are Terrace the Terrace Restaurant at London Zoo in London, England and the Coffee House in Nove Mesto nad Vagom, Slovakia.

The sixth type of urban planning placement is PLO on transport and pedestrian paths. The street and road network is always combined with the planning structure of the territory, providing convenient, fast and safe transport links to all functional areas and socially significant objects. Pedestrian communications (pedestrian roads, galleries, underground passages) are designed for the shortest possible connections between people and points of public concentration. As you can see in practice, PLO objects are placed not only in the centers of attraction for people, but also at

transport and pedestrian hubs. Examples include various eateries ("560" in Lisbon, Portugal), coffee shops ("Starbucks" in Fukuoka, Japan), fast food outlets ("The Wienerwald" in Munich, Germany) located on busy streets and highways. It is already common to place a PLO at public transport stops and major transport interchanges.

The seventh type of urban planning placement is PLO under reconstruction conditions. Due to the density of development in the central part of the city, it is common to place PLOS in premises that initially have a different function. The first and ground floors of residential buildings or free-standing public buildings are undergoing reconstruction. The main difficulty of such an arrangement is the development of an optimal planning structure of the premises of a public catering facility in accordance with the production technology. In the city, this is the most common and cost-effective type, the owner only bears the cost of interior design, communications, Parking and landscaping are always present. Examples include the Beton restaurant in Kiev, Ukraine, Origo and the Origo Coffeeshop in Bucharest, Romania.

The eighth type of urban planning placement is a non-standard location of the PLO. The practice of non-standard placement of public catering enterprises is still in its infancy. Having considered a variety of modern public catering enterprises, we can conclude that often the public is being held not so much by the variety of the menu, but by the unusual nature of the cafe, bar or restaurant. Great competition in this service sector generates

unusual locations and ways to attract visitors. For example, the tree restaurant Jemmas Sea View Kitchen, located on the island of Tobago, and the restaurant at the foot of the waterfall The Ville Escudero Resort, Philippines.

The ninth type of urban planning placement is mobile PLO. Such public catering facilities are vans, carts, and bicycles that sell food from. They are widespread in Europe, America and China, but in Russia this sphere is only being formed and covers only large cities so far. Most mobile PLOS are based in parks and city squares, and some are attached to sports and entertainment facilities. Theoretically, they should move around the city, but in reality they are tied to a specific place. As an example, we can mention the car "Gifts of Nature", located in Moscow. Throughout the summer, he appeared at various city festivals and fairs, offering visitors fast food dishes.

Conclusion. Public catering facilities are an integral part of the structure of modern public buildings and complexes, as well as urban and suburban spaces. In this paper, based on a statistical analysis of modern public catering facilities built after 2009, criteria are developed for determining the type of urban planning placement associated with both the characteristics of the public catering facility and the specifics and feasibility of its location in the settlement environment.

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